

TECHNOLOGIES OF EDUCATION OF BEHAVIOR AND ATTITUDE ETHICS THROUGH THE USE OF INFORMATION-RESOURCES IN SOCIAL COMMUNICATION IN PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Based on the analysis of sources, the content and essence and structure of the education of students and students through the use of information-resources are studied. the definition is adopted and the description of the structure of information content is given. The use of information-resources and the use of the project method in the formation of the technologies of education and treatment, relationship education were discussed.*

Keywords: *competence, information, information and communication technologies, project method, school.*

In the **introduction** of the article, the principles of socio-economic development of our Republic in the current period require to further increase our spiritual potential and economic power, to take a worthy place among the developed countries of the world, and to reconstruct them in a way that meets the requirements of the scientific and technical development of the 21st century. For this, it is necessary to change the outlook of our youth, to raise their knowledge and spirituality to the level of world standards. As we know, problem-based education has a special place in modern educational technology. At the heart of problem-based learning technology, or a chain of interrelated problems. Today, the society has set a task for the school: to develop their special ability, their independent knowledge in accordance with the purpose.

Problem-based educational technology takes a leading place in solving these tasks. This period is usually referred to as the school period of childhood. The important part of this period is that the child's personal experience, language skills, and knowledge acquired in the kindergarten age begin to be organized, and he begins to develop and grow up intellectually, morally, and socially.

The current era places great demands on teachers and students the most important requirements are the efficiency of the lesson, its quality, and the students knowledge and skills, various educational activities in schools, their organization and through it students acquire various knowledge and skills.

Today, it is innovative in organizing the educational process correctly and efficiently the role of technologies, technical tools, including modern computers is incomparable. Multimedia, animation, graphics, slides and the use of video films will help make the teaching process more interesting gives, and for this the teacher should work on himself and "I how he enters today's lesson process with something new and organizes the lesson interestingly. School for the development of social activity of a child of junior school age is one of the strategic directions of education modernization.

The personality of a child of primary school age in relation to the teacher's parents has a great impact on development. In particular, his outlook is vital positive or negative impact of the position and attitude towards children on the personality of the student can show. Because in primary education, education and upbringing are especially different is a process closely related to Junior school age includes the period from 6-7 to 9-10 years. During this period, the child is going through the period of junior school, that is, the period of primary school. During this period, it is necessary to increase the child's interest in studying and school, to be able to instill love for him. One of the most important characteristics of children of primary school age is that they have their own needs. [1]

In addition to these needs, the presence of a child's portfolio (personal cabinet), school supplies, bookshelf, desk and similar items increases his interest and desire to go to school like adults. Taking into account the fact that our time is developing rapidly in terms of technology, there is a person who feels inclined to various needs for the rest of his life. As we know, the process of going to school is defined from the age of 7. Because at this time, the child's brain is well developed, he will be at an age where he can perceive the surrounding signals, news, and changes well. At this point, if we give a brief opinion about the process of admitting a child to school, at this time the child's mental, physical and mental processes are checked. Only when a positive result is obtained from them, the child is admitted to school. However, due to the wishes of many parents, the child goes to school early. This also has its own good and bad sides. Of course, the sooner one starts pursuing knowledge, the better. However, sometimes mental stress is observed in the psyche of children of this age, as a result of which we can see that the child is tired, cannot attend classes well, and cannot finish homework. [3]

In fact, each child's growth period is different. Therefore, it is necessary to prepare the child psychologically for school. Because it is not easy for a child who grew up freely among his friends and toys in kindergarten to learn different rules and obligations. As the time for the child to go to school approaches, it is necessary to make sure that he is physically, mentally and motivationally mature. In this regard, in the process of preparing the child for school education, using modern information resources as an educational tool, various fairy tales and story books, children's TV channels have educational value.

Allowing to see the program helps the child to form thinking and speaking culture. For information: the weight of a 6-7-year-old child starts to grow up to 150-200 grams and height up to 0.5 centimeters per month. During this period, it is necessary to pay attention to the child's ability to see, hear and hold the spine correctly. Development of social activity of children of primary school age is one of the strategic directions of modernization of school education. A teacher has a great influence on the development of the personality of a child of primary school age compared to parents. In particular, his outlook, life position and attitude towards children can have a positive or negative impact on the personality of the student. As we know, junior school age is the period from 6-8 to 10-11 years old, they are preparatory groups for school education, primary school students. During these periods, important changes occur in the child's life and activities. Consequently, there will be significant changes in their psyche. A child's entry into school is a turning point in his life. As soon as the child enters school and starts studying, the main activity in his life is studying. Because primary education and upbringing are closely related processes. Due to the fact that almost all subjects are conducted by one pedagogue in primary education, their personal characteristics - morals, culture, pedagogical ability, attitude towards

children and even character traits are observed to be absorbed into the personal and moral qualities of children of primary school age. This is especially noticeable when compared to parallel classes.

This situation can continue in children of junior school age until they move to higher classes. Also, it is natural for 7-9-year-old elementary school students to follow their instructions in addition to pedagogues, as they need the help of their elderly grandparents in their families. Psychological features such as believing in the truth of every knowledge taught by the teacher by children of junior school age, imitating them, and fulfilling assigned tasks with love and affection are one of the important conditions of primary education. At the same time, these features are considered a process related to the formation of the first moral and cultural qualities in children's education. This period is usually referred to as the school period of childhood. The important part of this period is that the child's personal experience, language skills, and knowledge acquired in the kindergarten age begin to be organized, and he begins to develop and grow up intellectually, morally, and socially. [4]

According to Jean Piaget, a psychologist from Geneva, sharp turns occur in the intellectual potential of a 6-7-year-old child. His memory is much better, he falls into a certain system, order, now he remembers more and more what he wants. That is why they quickly solve the abstract mathematical problems that their parents think about, just like their teacher taught them. A child who has been listening to various fairy tales begins to understand the external real world as it is. The junior school period lasts from 6-7 to 9-10 years old, they get acquainted with various requirements for children of junior school age, they are biologically and psychologically prepared to learn the basics of science. His psyche develops enough to acquire knowledge. Sharpness, clarity, purity, accuracy of perception of a child of this age; differs from children of other ages due to his curiosity, trustworthiness, brightness of imagination, strength of memory, clarity of thinking. In a child preparing for school education, attention is relatively long-term and conditionally stable. "The main activity of children of primary school age is reading." A child's going to school plays an extremely important role in his psychological development and the formation of his personality. Under the guidance of the teacher, the child learns the content of various basic forms of human consciousness and learns to act on the basis of human traditions. [5]

In educational activities, the child exercises his will to achieve educational goals, requires the child to develop his speech, attention, memory, imagination and thinking to the required level, and creates new conditions for the development of the child's personality. A child who comes to school for the first time enters into a new system of psychological relations with those around him. He said that his life has changed radically, he has new obligations. he begins to feel burdened not only to go to school every day, but also to obey the demands of the academic profession. The fact that the family members are interested in the child's educational activities and achievements, as well as the fact that they control him, the new treatment and attitude towards him is the basis for his full feeling that his social status has changed, and for the change in his attitude towards himself. . Adults teach children to study, play, go for a walk and do other things. So, in the family, the child occupies a new place where he is counted and consulted. A student's success at school is a completely positive basis for his further mental development and personality formation. The child occupies a special place in the system of human relations, parents, relatives, and those around him may respect him not as a young child, but as a child who has his own tasks and obligations, according to the results of his activities. are treated as a separate person. As a result, it can be seen that the child begins to understand his place in his family, class and other communities.

During this period, the child's motive "I want this" begins to prevail over the motive "I must do this". Mental stress increases in every student who enters the first grade at school. This is manifested not only in his physical health, but also in his behavior, i.e., to a certain extent, in the increase of fear, decrease in voluntary activity. By this time, the child has achieved certain results in interaction with others, knows exactly what he wants and his place in his family. Also, he will have the skills of self-management, he will be able to work depending on the situation and situation. Behaviors and motives of children at this age are based on their self-evaluations, not "I am a good child", but these behaviors are seen by others. they begin to understand that it is evaluated according to how it is manifested in it.

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